

Enhanced Human Resource Practices on Work -Life Balance and Job Satisfaction Among Social Service Workers – A Structural Model Approach

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Vanitha, A. "Enhanced Human Resource Practices on Work - Life Balance and Job Satisfaction Among Social Service Workers – A Structural Model Approach." *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 17–26.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567675>

Dr. A. Vanitha

*Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, SCSVMV
Enathur, Kanchipuram*

Abstract

The study focused to test the role of enhanced human resource practices in social service sectors towards employees' work-life balance and job satisfaction. To test the model, 420 workers belonging to various social service organizations interviewed personally about their perception of enhanced human resource practices on their work-life balance and job satisfaction. The collected data were tested for conceptual model fit through AMOS 21.0 version. The outcome of the study divulges the intensity of human resource practices and its related strategies lead to work-life balance among the employees and also job satisfaction.

Keywords: Enhanced Human Resource Practices, Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, social service sector, structural equation model, AMOS

Introduction

Enhanced Human Resource Practices are the traditional term which is unified for modern requirements at work place for employee management. It is the combination of human resource management and development practices. The avenues of enhanced human resource practices include manpower planning, job analysis, recruitment, wage & salary administration, training and development, recognition & rewards, organizational support, mentoring and competency development. The various cross-sectional studies undertaken by the researchers about enhanced human resource practices reveal that the intensity of well-structured human resource practices with apt blend of resource planning and development will lead to employee motivation and commitment at work places.

Theoretical Background

In any entity, human resource (HR) practices are the direct investments on employees' human capital through which firms achieve competitive advantage and employees enhance their human capital. Recognizing the structure of HR practices comprised of

distinct patterns would maximize the chances to understand the firms’ ways of developing core competencies. Human resource management (HRM) is an important studying field in which much research attention has been given on creating core competencies, because of its “policies, practices, and systems that influence employees’ behaviour, attitudes and performance” (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart & Wright, 2000, p. 4). HR practices including recruitment, training, performance appraisal, and reward strategy are developed in the form of employee skills and organizational structures and employee motivation, and which are positively related to firm productivity and overall financial performance (Huselid, 1995). The work of Macduffie (1995) explored some bundle of innovative HR practices focusing on the firm’s economic performance and simultaneously classified these practices as employee skill and knowledge development and employee commitment and motivation generation. Edgar and Greare (2005) identified that HRM practices had a significant impact on employee attitudes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment and organizational fairness. Yu and Egri (2005) found that HR practices had a significant impact on the affective commitment of employees.

Problem Statement

The HRM function influences the employment relationship, through the psychological contract, and the beliefs held about mutual obligations and entitlements from both parties. Most Strategic HRM practices operate within the context of organisation culture that can significantly influence the psychological contract (**Harris & Ogbonna, 2001**). HRM interventions concern organization development techniques, aimed at how to attract, reward and develop competent people within the organization. Interventions are driven by the belief that better integration of the needs of the employees with that of the organization practices will facilitate greater organization effectiveness. Any HRM interventions to introduce formal WLB provisions, must not overlook the importance of informal workplace support, from supervisor as well as the organization climate itself (**Allen2001; Hammer et al. 2009**). The importance of HR interventions in selecting, training and developing supervisors to provide positive workplace social support to address job related as well as WLB issues, cannot be undermined. **Purcell et al. (2003:7)**, embarking on a CIPD study to “open the black box” presented a model that identified eleven important HR practices that feed into outcomes of “ability & skill”, “motivation & incentive”, and “opportunity to participate”. These mutually reinforcing practices are listed as training & development performance appraisal, job challenge/job autonomy, recruitment & selection, team working, involvement, communication, pay satisfaction, career opportunity, job security and work-life balance.

Social work is a discipline within human services. Its main goal is to assist individuals and families with their needs and solve their problems using a multidiscipline approach. In order to be effective, social workers work closely with many agencies and professionals. Social work provides an important service to society. Individuals and families in need of help are the focus of it, and are referred to as clients. Because our communities face a variety of problems, countries have realized that there is a need for social welfare services. This refers to formally organized, and socially sponsored institutions, agencies and programmes, to maintain or improve economic and social conditions, health or personal competence in some, or all, parts of the population. Social work activities are done through formalised structure through government, voluntary institution like NGOs and rehabilitation centres and so on. The individual who involve in social service activities need both commitment and organizational support for enhanced services to the needy, the institutions need to adopt effective human resource practices thus in turn influence employees satisfaction and commitment. But the avenues of human resource practices are so intensified in this activity, on that basis the enhanced human resource practices are required on training, competency

management, rewards and recognition as well as perceived cultural support. The work-life balance is the critical aspect need to study since the nature of work in social service activities are mostly family detached and insurmountably pressurised. In this aspect, the present study attempted to understand the role of enhanced human resource practices on work-life balance and job satisfaction among social work employees.

Literature Background

In a comparative study of HRM practices in India and Britain, **Budhwar and Khatri (2001)** found that different HRM practices like recruitment and selection, compensation practices, training practices, employee communication varied across the public and private sector organizations. The constant development of new and innovative human resource practices is necessary if an organization is to remain competitive (**Agarwala, 2003**). **Dhiman and Mohanty (2010)** in their research found that HRM practices like compensation, work-life balance, training, job content, career planning and empowerment enhance the commitment of employees towards their organization and impact turnover intentions. **De Vos and Meganck (2009)** in their study concluded that career opportunities and financial rewards as retention practices are regarded as a cause of employee turnover whereas the social environment, work-life balance and job design seems to positively affect employee retention. **Huang, Lin and Chuang (2006)** found that the status of being an honored employee, relative pay and promotion speed determined how long an employee would stay with their organization. **Ready et al. (2008)** found that (a) Purpose (guiding mission and goals, citizenship), (b) Culture (connection, authenticity), (c) Opportunity (challenging work, career track, competitive pay) and (d) Brand (known for excellence, inspirational leadership) are four pillars for attracting and retaining top talent. Work-life balance, work-family policies, flexible scheduling, dependent care benefits, human resource incentives (i.e., salary, job security, career development) and work design have also been identified as practices that enhance employee retention (**Batt & Valcour, 2003; Deery, 2008; Gächter, Savage & Torgler, 2013; Maxwell, 2005**). Compensation, work-life policies, training opportunities, career opportunities, supervisor support and job characteristics have been identified as factors of employee retention by **Döckel (2003)** and **Döckel, Basson and Coetzee (2006)**. *Recognition*, according to many studies, is a fundamental driver of human behavior, which emphasizes the provision of signals to workers in appreciating the quality of their work and achievements (**Paré and Tremblay, 2007; Yang, 2012**). *Fair reward* refers to workers feeling that their job outcomes, such as compensation conditions, performance evaluation, and job assignments, are fairly judged and rewarded accordingly (**Kehoe and Wright, 2013; Yang, 2012**). *Empowerment* refers to providing workers with opportunities to make their own decisions with regard to their job-related activities and to bear the responsibility for these decisions (**Chebat and Kollias, 2000**). Finally, *competence development* practices, such as training and mentoring, focus on “both improving the productivity of existing workers and sending workers the signal that decision makers are willing to invest in them beyond the short-term return” (**Graham and Tarbell, 2006; Paré and Tremblay, 2007**).

Objectives

- To describe the personal and professional profile of employees in social service activities
- To understand their interest on involving in social service activities
- To verify the role of enhanced human resource activities on work-life balance and job satisfaction among employees in social service institutions.

Hypotheses

There is an impact of enhanced human resource practices concerning recognition, competency management and perceived organizational support on work-life balance of employees in social service institution.

There is an indirect impact of enhance human resource practise like competency, recognition and perceived work place support on job satisfaction.

Work-life balance mediates enhanced human resource practices and job satisfaction

Figure 1 Proposed Conceptual Model

Research Method

The survey was undertaken among the social workers who are engaged in the activities of women security, orphanage protection, child labour abolishment, rehabilitation programme and donor organization. The respondents were chosen from both government supported and voluntarily network. The organizations which are operating around Chennai and others parts of Tamilnadu were contacted through personal and mail interview. Initially a pilot study was undertaken about the social service activities and employees problems, during the time of experience survey and informal depth interviews, it was identified selected human dimensions and its strategic execution have an impact on quality work-life and work-life balance of social service employees and subsequently on their job satisfaction. Based on the literature surveys and its reviews, it was identified that there are three important aspects like rewards & recognition, perceived organizational support and competency management are vital aspects of human resource practices in social service organization as an enhanced strategy along with traditional human resource avenues, subsequently its impact on work-life balance and job satisfaction are the critical aspects need to measure. A questionnaire with twenty one items with Likert Scale (1- strongly disagree to 5- strongly agree) to measure recognition, potential appraisal and competency. The four item scale related to work-life imbalance was taken from Hill et al. (2001). The five-item scale related to job satisfaction was taken from Price and Mueller (1986) to measure workers’ overall job satisfaction. Initially 30 items were pretested for its validity as well as reliability. The reliability of cronbach alpha for all the items were obtained above 0.75 (75 percent) through reliability analysis in SPSS 17.0. Further to that the validated questionnaire was distributed among the respondents and the required responses were collected. The collected data were tested for its missing value, normality and outlier, where in which 3 items in enhanced practices found to be out reached, after removing those items, the unidimensionality of five constructs were tested. During the testing of uni dimensionality, by verifying the standardised estimate (more than 0.5) and squared multiple correlation (more than 0.4) for five constructs, each construct was loaded with three items. The finalised items under each constructs were taken for measurement fit testing.

Structural Equation Model

As a series of interrelationship (between selected enhanced human resource practices, work-life balance and job satisfaction were to be explored and tested, SEM was treated as an appropriate data analysis tool. In connection to that, the primary research objective was to identify the effect of enhanced human resource practices on work-life balance and job satisfaction.. As indicated by Hair et al. SEM is an appropriate measurable procedure for building up and understanding the kind of connection between exogenous and endogenous construct.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics, Reliability and Correlation Matrix

Constructs	Mean	S.D	CRONBACH'S A	RCC	CDD	PSS	PAA	WLB	JSS
RCC	4.0990	.84344	.821	1	-	-	-	-	-
CDD	4.2630	.72502	.860	.276**	1	-	-	-	-
PSS	3.8863	1.02568	.792	.475**	.334**	1	-	-	-
PAA	3.7882	1.12427	.794	.500**	.230**	.583**	1	-	-
WLB	4.0408	.91013	.799	.531**	.269**	.603**	.591**	1	-
JSS	3.9089	1.05000	.802	.421**	.187**	.616**	.658**	.548**	1

*(Pearson) Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), ** (Pearson) Correlation is significant at the 0.1level (2-tailed)

(RCC-Recognition, CDD-Competency Development, PSS-Perceived Support, PAA-WLB-Work-life Balance, JSS-Job Satisfaction)

Confirming The Measurement Model Using CFA

After validation of the measurement instrument was satisfied, the results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using AMOS 17 was used to evaluate the model fit of the measurement model to confirm the hypothesized structure.

Measurement Model

The measurement model shown in figure 1 comprises of five factors. Each factor is measured by a minimum of three observed variables, the reliability of which is influenced by random measurement error, as indicated by the associated error term. Each of these observed variables is regressed into its respective factor. Finally all the five factors are shown to be inter-correlated.

Figure 2

RCC-Recognition, CDD-Competency Development, PSS-Perceived Support, PAA- Potential Appraisal WLB-Work-life Balance, JSS-Job Satisfaction

Table 2 Computation of Degrees of Freedom

Number of distinct sample moments	171
Number of distinct parameters to be estimated	51
Degrees of freedom (171-51)	120

The proposed model in this study is an over-identified model with positive degrees of freedom (120) as shown in table 3 drawn from the AMOS output. In this model there are 171 distinct sample moments (i.e., pieces of information) from which to compute the estimates of the default model, and 51 distinct parameters to be estimated, leaving 120 degrees of freedom, which is positive (greater than zero). Hence the model is an over identified one.

Table 3 Fit Indices of the Measurement Model

Fit Statistic	Recommended	Measurement Obtained
χ^2	-	239.363
Df	-	120
χ^2 significance	$p \leq 0.05$.000
χ^2/df	$\leq 2- 5.0$	1.995
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.937
AGFI	>0.80	0.910
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.872
RFI	≥ 0.90	0.837
CFI	≥ 0.95	0.931
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.911
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.051
RMR	≤ 0.05	0.071

Source: Hair et al. (2010), Hu and Bentler (1998), Becker et.al, (2013), and Evermann and Tate (2016).

Goodness of Fit attributes (GFI) obtained is 0.937 as against the recommended value of above 0.90. Adjusted Goodness of Fit attributes (AGFI) obtained is 0.910 as against the recommended value of above 0.80. The Normed fit Attributes (NFI), Relative Fit attributes (RFI) and Comparative Fit attributes (CFI), Tucker Lewis Attributes (TLI) are 0.872, 0.837, 0.931 and 0.911 respectively as against the recommended level of above 0.90.

RMSEA is 0.051 below the recommended limit of 0.08, and Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) is below the recommended limit of 0.05 at 0.01. This can be interpreted as meaning that the model explains the correlation to within an average error of 0.041 (Shah and Goldstein 2006). Hence the model shows an overall acceptable fit. The model is an over identified model.

The confirmatory factor analysis showed an acceptable overall model fit and hence, the theorized model fit well with the observed data. It can be concluded that the hypothesized five factor CFA model fits the sample data very well.

Structural Equation Modeling

In SEM Exogenous are correlated each other. There are three exogenous variable namely parking facility, Traffic flow, and Accessibility. There are two endogenous variables in the path diagram namely consumer patronage and Brand Image. In SEM Endogenous variable should have error terms. So there are two error terms namely e22 and e23. Endogenous variable are influenced by the exogenous variables in the model, either directly or indirectly.

Analysis of Structural Model

The results of the theoretical structural model indicated that the chi-square of 171 with 120 degree of freedom was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, indicating an inappropriate fit. However, it has been stated that the chi square is highly sensitive to sample size and usually suggests a poor fit with large sample sizes (Becker et.al, 2013).

Figure 3

NOTE: RCC-Recognition, CDD-Competency Development, PSS-Perceived Support, PAA- Potential Appraisal WLB-Work-life Balance, JSS-Job Satisfaction

Other fit statistics were within the acceptable values ($\chi^2/df = 1.995$; GFI= 0.937; AGFI=0.910; NFI=0.872; CFI=0.931; TLI= 0.911; RFI=0.837; RMSEA =0.051). Overall, the fit statistics indicated a high fit between the data and the theoretical model.

Figure 4 Path Diagram for The Theoretical Model

NOTE: RCC-Recognition, CDD-Competency Development, PSS-Perceived Support, PAA- Potential Appraisal WLB-Work-life Balance, JSS-Job Satisfaction.

Table 4

Hypotheses	Paths	Standard-ized (β)	S.e	C.r(t)	P	Result
H1: There is a significant direct effect of Recognition on Work-life Balance	WLB<---RCC	.247	.048	5.189	***	Supported
H2: There is a significant direct effect of competency development on Work-life Balance	WLB<--CDD	.043	.049	.882	.378	Not Supported
H3: there is a significant direct effect of potential appraisal on Work-life Balance	WLB<--PSS	.281	.042	6.649	***	Supported
H4: there is a significant direct effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction	WLB<--JSS	.230	.038	6.015	***	Supported
H5: There is a significant indirect effect of recognition on Job satisfaction	RCC<--JSS	.142	.057	2.501	.012	Supported
H6: There is a significant indirect effect of competency development on Job satisfaction	CDD<--JSS	.022	.055	.410	.682	Not supported
H7: There is a significant indirect effect of potential appraisal on Job satisfaction	PSS<--JSS	-.070	.055	-1.286	.198	Not supported
H8: work-life balance mediates between enhanced human resource practices and job satisfaction	EN<--WLB<--JSS	0.761	.055	0.328	0.002	supported

***Effect are significant at $p < 0.05$

Conclusion

The study focused to analyze the enhanced human resource practices like recognition, competency development and potential appraisal on work-life balance and its influence on job satisfaction among social service workers. The outcome of tested theoretical model reveals that the recognition and potential appraisal have direct effect on work-life balance whereas competency development does not have significant influence. In addition to that, the work-life balance helps the job satisfaction of the employees in social service workers and potential appraisal sometimes effects directly on job satisfaction without having the mediation of work-life balance. However, at the same time the other enhanced human resource practices like recognition and potential appraisal depends on work-life balance via through the job satisfaction.

References

1. Doucet, O., Lapalme, M-E., Simard, G., and Trembley, M. (2015). *High involvement management practices as leadership enhancers*. International Journal of Manpower, 36(7), 1058-1071.
2. Nishil, L.H., Lepak, D.P. and Schneider, B. (2008). *Employee attributions of the “why” of HR practices: Their effects on employee attitudes and behaviors, and customer satisfaction*. Personnel Psychology, 61(3), 503-544.

3. Jiang, K., Lepak, D.P., Hu, J., and Baer, J.C. (2012). *How does human resource management influence organizational outcomes? A meta-analytic investigation of mediating mechanisms.* Academy of Management Journal, 55(6), 1264-1294.
4. Gould-Williams, J. (2007). *HR practices, organizational climate and employee outcomes: evaluating social exchange relationships in local government.* International Journal of Human Resource Management, 18(9), 1627-1647.
5. Gould-Williams, J., and Davies, F. (2005). *Using social exchange theory to predict the effects of HRM practice on employee outcomes: An analysis of public sector workers.* Public Management Review, 7(1), 1-24.
6. Ramsay, H., Scholarios, D., and Harley, B. (2000). *Employees and high-performance work systems: Testing inside the black box.* British Journal of Industrial Relations, 38(4), 501- 531.
7. Straker, J.K., and Atchley, R.C. (1999). *Recruiting and retaining frontline workers in longterm care: Usual organizational practices in Ohio.* Oxford, OH: Scripps Gerontology Center. Su, S., Baird, K.,
8. Gregory, A., and Milner, S. (2009). *Editorial: work–life balance: A matter of choice? Gender, Work and Organization*, 16(1), 1-13.
9. Harley, B., Allen, B.C., and Sargent, L.D. (2007). *High performance work systems and employee experience of work in the service sector: The case of aged care.* British Journal of Industrial Relations, 45(3), 607-633.
10. Harley, B., Sargent, L.D., and Allen, B.C. (2010). *Employee responses to ‘high performance work system’ practices: An empirical test of the disciplined worker thesis.* Work, Employment and Society, 24(4), 740-760.
11. Tietjen, M.A., and Myers, R.M. (1998). *Motivation and job satisfaction.* Management Decision, 36(4), 226-231.
12. Wright, T.A., and Bonett, D.G. (2002). *The moderating effects of employee tenure on the relation between organizational commitment and job performance: A meta-analysis.* Journal of Applied Psychology, 87(6), 1183-1190.
13. MacDuffie, J.P. (1995). *Human resource bundles and manufacturing performance: Organizational logic and flexible production systems in the world auto industry.* Industrial and Labor Relations Review, 48: 197-221
14. Yu, B. B., Egri, C. P. (2005). *Human resource management practices and affective organizational commitment: A comparison of Chinese employees in a state-owned enterprise and a joint venture.* Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources, 43(3), 332-360
15. Harris, B. R., Huselid, M. A., & Becker, B. E. (1999). *Strategic human resource management at Praxair.* Human Resource Management, 38(4), 315–320.
16. Harris, L., & Ogbonna, E. (2001). *Strategic human resource management, market orientation, and organizational performance.* Journal of Business Research, 51(2), 157–166
17. Edgar, F., Geare, A., *HRM practice and employee attitudes: Different measure s-different results.* Personnel Review, Vol.34, No.5, pp. 534-549, 2005.
18. Harris, L & Ogbonna, E. (2001) *Strategic Human Resource Management, Market Orientation and Organizational Performance.* Journal of Business Research. Issue 51 pp 157-166.
19. Rowley C. & Abdul-Rahman S. (2008). *The Changing Face of Management in South East Asia.* London & New York.
20. Routledge. Rowley C. Abdul Rahman S. (2007) *The Management of Human Resources in Malaysia: Locally-owned Companies and Multinational Companies.* Management Revue. Vol 18 Issue 4. pp. 374-391.

21. Rowley, J. (1996) *Motivation and academic staff in higher education*. *Quality Assurance in Education* Vol. 4 No.3 pp.11–16
22. Allen T. D. (2001). *Family-supportive work environments: The role of organizational perceptions*. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 58, 414–435.
23. Allen, T.D., Herst, D.E., Bruck, C.S. & Sutton, M. (2000). *Consequences associated with work to family conflict: A review and agenda for future research*. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 5, pp.278-308.
24. Budhwar, P. 1999. ‘*Taking Human Resource Management Research to the Next Millennium: Need for an Integrated Framework*’, Paper Presented at the Annual Academy of Management Conference, 9-11 August 1999, Chicago
25. Dhiman, G. R., & Mohanty, R. P. (2010). *HRM Practices, Attitudinal Outcomes and Turnover Intent: An Empirical Study in Indian Oil and Gas Exploration and Production Sector*. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 17(4), 74-104.
26. De Vos, A., Buyens, D, & Schalk, R. (2003). “*Psychological contract development during organizational socialization: Adaptation to reality and the role of reciprocity*”, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24(5), 537-599.
27. Huang, I., Lin, H., & Chuang, C. (2006). “*Constructing factors related to worker retention*. *International Journal of Manpower*”, 27(5), 491-508.
28. Batt, R. 2000. “*Managing Customer Services: Human Resource Practices, Quit Rates, and Sales Growth*”. Working Paper 00-07. Center for Advanced Human Resource Studies, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY.